

A Descriptive-Correlational Study on the Mastery Level of Least Learned Competencies and Academic Performance of Grade 5 Learners in Araling Panlipunan at Mangagoy East Elementary School, Bislig City Division: Basis for a Contextualized Remediation Program

Jean Consigna Palma^{1*} and Rio S. Consigna²

¹Teacher II, Mangagoy East Elementary School, Bislig City Division, Surigao del Sur, Philippines

²Colleges of Bislig

jean.palma002@deped.gov.ph

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the mastery level of least learned competencies and academic performance of Grade 5 learners in Araling Panlipunan at Mangagoy East Elementary School, Bislig City Division, as basis for a contextualized remediation program. A quantitative descriptive-correlational design using documentary analysis was employed. The study analyzed valid learner records from quarterly assessment results, item analysis, and report card grades. Frequency, percentage, mean percentage score, ranking, and Pearson product-moment correlation were used to treat the data. Findings showed that learners obtained an overall Mean Percentage Score of 68.35, interpreted as Nearly Proficient. The majority of learners were also classified as Nearly Proficient, while seven competencies were identified as least learned, with mastery percentages

ranging from 29.27% to 43.90%, all interpreted as Low Mastery. The lowest mastery was recorded in identifying the origin of the Philippines based on science, folk knowledge, and religion. Despite these competency gaps, the learners' final academic performance in Araling Panlipunan was generally Very Satisfactory, with a final mean grade of 86.68. Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant strong positive relationship between overall assessment MPS and final AP grade, $r = 0.708$, $p < .001$. The study concludes that mastery level is significantly associated with academic performance and that general grades may not fully show specific competency gaps. A contextualized remediation program is recommended to support reteaching, guided practice, localized examples, and assessment-based instructional intervention.

Keywords: *academic performance, Araling Panlipunan, contextualized remediation, item analysis, least learned competencies, mastery level*

INTRODUCTION

Every learner's score provides evidence of what has been understood, what remains difficult, and what needs to be taught again. In basic education, assessment data are important because they help teachers move beyond general impressions and identify specific learning gaps. This concern is relevant internationally because

global reports continue to show that access to schooling does not always result in adequate learning, particularly in reading, reasoning, and foundational skills (UNESCO, 2024; World Bank et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, assessment results also indicate persistent learning challenges. Filipino learners performed below the OECD average in the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment, and only 24% reached at least Level 2 proficiency in reading (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2023b). Although PISA does not directly assess Araling Panlipunan, the low performance in reading and reasoning-related domains is highly relevant because AP requires learners to interpret texts, analyze historical and social information, explain relationships, and make informed judgments.

Classroom assessment is therefore a crucial mechanism for instructional improvement. DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015 states that classroom assessment is integral to curriculum implementation because it allows teachers to track learners' progress and adjust instruction accordingly (Department of Education [DepEd], 2015). In this sense, quarterly examination results, item analysis, Table of Specifications, E-Class Record, and report card grades are not merely records for grading; they are data sources that can identify mastery level, least learned competencies, and needed remediation.

Araling Panlipunan is a significant learning area because it develops learners' understanding of history, society, culture, citizenship, geography, governance, and social responsibility. The K to 12 Araling Panlipunan curriculum aims to form learners who are critical, reflective, responsible, productive, environmentally aware, nationalistic, and humane (DepEd, 2016b). When learners show low mastery in AP competencies, the issue affects not only subject grades but also their development as informed and responsible citizens.

In Bislig City Division, Mangagoy East Elementary School serves as the immediate context of this study. Publicly available data do not provide school-level information on the least learned competencies of Grade 5 learners in Araling Panlipunan; therefore, the most relevant evidence comes from the school's own Grade 5 AP quarterly assessment results, item analysis, and report card grades. This study examined those records to determine learners' mastery level, identify least learned competencies, determine academic performance, test the relationship between mastery level and academic performance, and develop a contextualized remediation program responsive to the actual needs of the learners.

Literature Review

Least Learned Competencies in Araling Panlipunan

Least learned competencies refer to specific skills or concepts where learners show low mastery based on assessment results. In Araling Panlipunan, these may include difficulty explaining historical significance, interpreting events, understanding civic responsibilities, and analyzing social or cultural relationships. The NCSS definition of social studies emphasizes civic life, people, systems, and interactions across time and place, which aligns with the goals of Araling Panlipunan (National Council for the Social Studies, n.d.).

The global and ASEAN perspectives reinforce the need to examine competency mastery. UNESCO's Global Citizenship Education framework emphasizes local, national, and global systems, identity, diversity, responsibility, and participation (UNESCO, 2015b), while the ASEAN Curriculum Sourcebook highlights cultural identity, diversity, equity, justice, sustainability, and regional awareness (ASEAN Secretariat & SEAMEO, 2012). These perspectives show that AP competencies are not limited to factual recall but include understanding, interpretation, and responsible social participation.

Identifying least learned competencies is essential because report card grades may not reveal the exact skills that learners failed to master. Item analysis helps determine which test items and competencies were difficult for learners, allowing teachers to prioritize reteaching and remediation. The University of Washington (n.d.) explains that item difficulty shows the proportion of learners who answered an item correctly and can be used to identify areas where learning did not occur sufficiently.

Classroom Assessment, Item Analysis, and Academic Performance

Classroom assessment provides evidence that guides teachers in adjusting instruction. DepEd (2015) emphasizes that classroom assessment is part of curriculum implementation because it tracks progress and informs teaching decisions. This view is consistent with the formative assessment perspective of Black and Wiliam (1998), who argued that assessment supports learning when teachers use results to give feedback and modify instruction.

Item analysis offers more specific diagnostic information than grades alone. Rezigalla (2022) describes item analysis as a process for examining item difficulty, discrimination, and response patterns. In the context of Araling Panlipunan, item analysis can reveal whether learners struggle with historical reasoning, cause-and-effect explanations, interpretation of maps or texts, or understanding civic concepts. Such information helps teachers design remediation based on actual learning gaps.

Academic performance, represented by report card grades, remains important because it summarizes learners' achievement across grading periods. However, grades should be interpreted together with mastery and item-analysis results. A learner may receive a satisfactory or very satisfactory grade while still having low mastery in particular competencies. This is why the present study examined both mastery level and academic performance and tested the relationship between the two.

Contextualized Remediation and Mastery Learning

Contextualized remediation is aligned with the principle that instruction should be responsive to learners' needs, experiences, and social context. Republic Act No. 10533 supports a curriculum that is learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally appropriate, culture-sensitive, contextualized, and global (Republic Act No. 10533, 2013). In Araling Panlipunan, contextualization may involve local examples, community issues, familiar stories, maps, timelines, picture analysis, and guided discussion linked to learners' own environment.

Mastery learning supports the use of corrective activities when learners do not yet fully understand important competencies. The Education Endowment Foundation (n.d.) explains that mastery learning gives learners additional time and support before moving forward. Guskey (2010) similarly emphasized that formative assessment should be followed by corrective activities that guide learners toward mastery. In the present study, contextualized remediation is designed as the corrective response to identified least learned competencies.

Local and related studies further support the development of contextualized instructional support in Araling Panlipunan. Lorbis (2019) studied contextualized teaching and learning in Araling Panlipunan, while Jalotjot and Fidelino (2023) validated contextualized and localized modules in Araling Panlipunan 9. Ventura and Gutierrez (2024) likewise examined strategies for contextualizing the Araling Panlipunan curriculum. These studies affirm that contextualized materials can make social studies concepts more meaningful and accessible to learners.

Figure 1. *Conceptual framework of the study*

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design using documentary analysis. The descriptive component was used to determine the mastery level, least learned competencies, and academic performance of Grade 5 learners in Araling Panlipunan. The correlational component was used to determine the relationship between mastery level and academic performance. Documentary analysis was appropriate because the study used existing school records such as quarterly assessment results, item analysis, and report card grades rather than administering a new test to the learners.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Mangagoy East Elementary School, Bislig City Division, Surigao del Sur, Philippines. The school is listed in the DepEd National Inventory Dashboard under Bislig City, Caraga, with School ID 132834. The local setting was appropriate because the study focused on the actual Grade 5 Araling Panlipunan assessment records of the school and used these data as basis for a contextualized remediation program.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The study analyzed the valid records of Grade 5 learners in Araling Panlipunan. Complete enumeration was used for the available learner records included in the final computation. The results tables reported 40 learner-level records for mastery-level distribution, academic performance, and correlation analysis. Learners' names and personal identifiers were not included in the manuscript; only summarized assessment and grade data were used.

Table 1. *Data Sources Used in the Study*

Data source	Purpose in the study	Statistical use
Quarterly assessment results	Determine overall and quarterly mastery level	Mean Percentage Score and interpretation
Item analysis	Identify least learned competencies	Frequency, percentage, mastery percentage, and ranking
Report card grades	Describe academic performance in Araling Panlipunan	Mean grade and performance distribution
Learner-level MPS and final AP grade	Test association between mastery and academic performance	Pearson product-moment correlation

Research Instrument

The study used documentary analysis instruments prepared by the researcher to organize existing assessment records. These included a Quarterly Test Performance Record Sheet, Documentary Analysis Matrix, Competency Mapping Checklist, and Contextualized Remediation Planning Matrix. The instruments were used to record quarterly scores, connect test items with Grade 5 Araling Panlipunan competencies, identify low-mastery competencies, and prepare remediation activities based on the findings.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was secured from the school head before the learner records were reviewed. The researcher examined the Grade 5 Araling Panlipunan quarterly assessment results, item analysis, Table of Specifications, E-Class Record, and report card grades. Learner names were coded to protect identity. The data were organized by quarter, score, percentage, competency, and interpretation. Competencies with low mastery percentages were ranked and used as priority areas for the contextualized remediation program.

Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage were used to describe mastery-level and performance-level distributions. Mean and Mean Percentage Score were used to determine quarterly and overall mastery level. Ranking was used to arrange the least learned competencies according to mastery percentage. Pearson product-moment correlation was

used to determine the relationship between overall assessment MPS and final AP grade. The level of significance was set at .05.

Ethical Consideration

The study used existing school records and did not require the administration of a new test. Permission to access assessment records was secured from the appropriate school authority. Learner identities were protected through coding, and only aggregated data were reported. The study observed confidentiality, responsible data handling, and non-disclosure of personal learner information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mastery Level Based on Quarterly Assessment Results

The learners obtained an overall Mean Percentage Score of 68.35 in Araling Panlipunan, interpreted as Nearly Proficient. The quarterly MPS showed improvement from 60.50 in the first quarter to 74.05 in the fourth quarter. Although the fourth-quarter result approached the Mastered/Proficient range, the overall result indicates that many learners still needed reinforcement and guided practice.

Table 2. *Mastery Level of Learners Based on Quarterly Assessment Results*

Quarter	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Interpretation
First Quarter	60.50	Nearly Proficient
Second Quarter	69.25	Nearly Proficient
Third Quarter	69.60	Nearly Proficient
Fourth Quarter	74.05	Nearly Proficient
Overall	68.35	Nearly Proficient

The distribution of learners further supports this finding. Most learners were in the Nearly Proficient level, showing that the class had partial mastery but still required additional instructional support. Only one learner reached Very High Mastery, while five learners remained at the Low Mastery level.

Table 3. *Distribution of Learners by Overall Mastery Level*

Mastery level	Frequency	Percentage
Very High Mastery	1	2.50%
Mastered/Proficient	10	25.00%
Nearly Proficient	24	60.00%
Low Mastery	5	12.50%
Very Low Mastery	0	0.00%
Total	40	100.00%

Least Learned Competencies Based on Item Analysis

The item analysis identified seven least learned Grade 5 Araling Panlipunan competencies. All seven competencies were interpreted as Low Mastery, with mastery percentages ranging from 29.27% to 43.90%. The lowest mastery was recorded in identifying the origin of the Philippines based on science, folk knowledge, and religion. The findings indicate that learners had difficulty with competencies requiring explanation, analysis, comparison, historical reasoning, and understanding of abstract civic-historical concepts.

Table 4. *Least Learned Competencies Based on Item Analysis*

Rank	Quarter	Code	Competency focus	Correct/No. of learners	Mastery %	Interpretation
1	Q1	APQ1-C3	Origin of the Philippines based on science, folk knowledge, and religion	12/41	29.27	Low Mastery
2	Q3	AP5-Q3-C3	Spanish colonial policies implemented in the country	13/41	31.71	Low Mastery
3	Q4	AP5-Q4-C5	Cavite Mutiny, GOMBURZA, and the rise of Filipino nationalism	14/41	34.15	Low Mastery
4	Q2	AP5Q2-C2	Beliefs, religion, and traditions of ancient Filipinos	15/41	36.59	Low Mastery
5	Q1	AP5Q1-C7	Role of women in the development of ancient Filipino culture	16/41	39.02	Low Mastery
6	Q3	AP5-Q3-C6	Efforts of indigenous groups, women, and other sectors to defend freedom from colonialism	17/41	41.46	Low Mastery
7	Q4	AP5-Q4-C4	Secularization and Filipinization of parishes	18/41	43.90	Low Mastery

These competencies are historically and conceptually demanding because they require learners to understand social causes, historical consequences, cultural roles, political movements, and abstract terms. The results support the need for remediation that uses visual materials, local examples, guided reading, timelines, role-play, and cause-and-effect organizers to make difficult AP concepts more concrete.

Academic Performance Based on Report Card Grades

The learners' final mean grade in Araling Panlipunan was 86.68, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. The first, second, and third quarters were all Very Satisfactory, while the fourth quarter reached Outstanding with a mean grade of 90.43. This suggests improvement in report card performance toward the end of the school year.

Table 5. *Academic Performance Based on Report Card Grades*

Grading period	Mean grade	Interpretation
First Quarter Grade	85.38	Very Satisfactory
Second Quarter Grade	85.38	Very Satisfactory
Third Quarter Grade	85.55	Very Satisfactory
Fourth Quarter Grade	90.43	Outstanding
Final AP Grade	86.68	Very Satisfactory

In terms of final academic performance, 30.00% of learners obtained Outstanding performance, another 30.00% obtained Very Satisfactory performance, 35.00% were Satisfactory, and 5.00% were Fairly Satisfactory. No learner was classified under Did Not Meet Expectations. This pattern shows that the class generally performed well in report card grades; however, the least learned competencies reveal that grades alone may not fully identify exact skills requiring intervention.

Table 6. *Distribution of Learners by Final Academic Performance*

Performance level	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	12	30.00%
Very Satisfactory	12	30.00%
Satisfactory	14	35.00%
Fairly Satisfactory	2	5.00%
Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0.00%
Total	40	100.00%

Relationship Between Mastery Level and Academic Performance

The Pearson product-moment correlation result showed a significant strong positive relationship between learners' overall assessment MPS and final AP grade. The computed r-value was 0.708 with a p-value lower than .001. Since the p-value was below the .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that learners with higher mastery based on assessment results also tended to obtain higher report card grades in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 7. *Correlation Between Mastery Level and Academic Performance*

Variables correlated	n	Test used	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Overall Assessment MPS and Final AP Grade	40	Pearson r	0.708	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant strong positive relationship

This finding supports the conclusion that improving learners' mastery of competencies may help strengthen academic performance. It also confirms the practical value of analyzing assessment records because the mastery level provides a more competency-specific view of learner performance than final grades alone.

Proposed Contextualized Remediation Program

Based on the findings, the proposed contextualized remediation program prioritizes the seven identified least learned competencies. The program uses localized examples, picture analysis, guided reading, timelines, cause-and-effect organizers, story mapping, role-play, group work, and formative assessment. It may be implemented during scheduled intervention periods or after quarterly assessment analysis.

Table 8. *Proposed Contextualized Remediation Program*

Priority	Competency focus	Contextualized activity/strategy	Materials needed	Assessment/monitoring
1	Origin of the Philippines	Larawan Ko, Kuwento Mo: learners draw and explain scientific, folk, and religious explanations.	Pictures, Manila paper, activity sheets	Short quiz and oral explanation
2	Spanish colonial policies	Cause-and-effect chart showing how colonial policies affected Filipino communities.	Timeline cards, chart, local examples	Exit ticket and worksheet
3	Cavite Mutiny and GOMBURZA	Picture-based inquiry and timeline of events leading to Filipino nationalism.	Pictures, timeline strips, guide questions	Post-test and group presentation
4	Ancient beliefs and traditions	Community tradition web comparing ancient beliefs with familiar local practices.	Story cards, pictures, local examples	Concept map and short quiz
5	Role of women in ancient society	Picture analysis and role chart on women's contributions in early society.	Pictures, role cards, worksheet	Role chart and reflection
6	Defense of freedom from colonialism	Gallery walks and group reporting on groups that resisted colonialism.	Gallery cards, reading strips	Group output and rubric
7	Secularization and Filipinization	Guided timeline and role-play to explain the movement in learner-friendly language.	Timeline, role cards, guide questions	Short quiz and reflection

The program is contextualized because it connects AP competencies to learners' familiar experiences and community examples. Its monitoring tools include short quizzes, worksheets, oral explanations, exit tickets, group outputs, post-tests, and follow-up item analysis. In this way, assessment results become a basis not only for reporting performance but also for planning responsive instruction.

CONCLUSION

The Grade 5 learners were generally Nearly Proficient in Araling Panlipunan based on quarterly assessment results. Although their MPS improved from the first quarter to the fourth quarter, the overall mastery level still indicated the need for reinforcement, guided practice, and targeted remediation.

The identified least learned competencies showed that learners had difficulty in historical explanation, analysis of social and cultural concepts, cause-and-effect relationships, and abstract civic-historical topics. These areas require focused remediation and more concrete learning experiences that use visual, localized, participatory, and learner-centered activities.

The learners demonstrated Very Satisfactory academic performance based on report card grades. However, the presence of low-mastery competencies shows that general grades may not fully reveal the specific Araling Panlipunan competencies that learners have not mastered. The significant strong positive relationship between overall assessment MPS and final AP grade confirms that mastery level is closely associated with academic performance. Thus, strengthening learners' mastery of least learned competencies may contribute to improved academic performance in Araling Panlipunan.

Recommendation

Grade 5 Araling Panlipunan teachers should regularly conduct item analysis after every quarterly examination to identify least learned competencies and determine which lessons require reteaching, reinforcement, or enrichment. Assessment results should be discussed during instructional planning and should serve as evidence for classroom-based remediation.

Teachers should implement contextualized remediation activities that use local examples, visual materials, timelines, maps, picture analysis, guided reading, storytelling, role-play, group work, and cause-and-effect organizers. These activities may help learners understand historical and civic concepts more clearly by connecting them with familiar and concrete experiences.

The proposed contextualized remediation program should be implemented, monitored, and evaluated using pre-tests, post-tests, worksheets, short quizzes, oral explanations, exit tickets, group outputs, and follow-up item analysis. School administrators should support the implementation by providing time for intervention sessions, learning resources, technical assistance, and opportunities for teachers to discuss item analysis results during Learning Action Cell sessions.

Parents and guardians should be informed about learners' areas of difficulty so they can provide encouragement and simple review support at home. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in other grade levels, schools, or learning areas and may include pre-test and post-test data, teacher interviews, learner feedback, or experimental designs to determine the effectiveness of the proposed remediation program.

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